

STUDIES ON THE RATE OF COAGULATION AND ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL OF LANTHANUM OXIDE HYDROSOL

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The coagulation of lanthanum oxide sol and its dependence on electrokinetic potential have been studied. The true electrokinetic potential, ζ , has been evaluated by applying a surface conductance correction with the help of the equation:

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m \cdot \frac{1}{S}$$

(where ζ_a represents the apparent electrokinetic potential calculated from electrokinetic data using Smoluchowski's equation, m is a constant involving surface conductance and other terms, and S represents the specific conductivity in bulk of the intermicellar fluid containing equicoagulating concentration of an electrolyte).

It has been found that in the regions of slow and rapid coagulation the values of true ζ -potential are 35.1 mv and 32.2 mv respectively.

It has been shown previously (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 273, 394; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 955) that in the presence of equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes containing counter ions of different valency, the true ζ -potential can be found from electro-osmotic data by using the equation:

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + m \cdot \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where ζ_a represents the electrokinetic potential calculated from the Smoluchowski equation; ζ , the true electrokinetic potential; S , the specific conductivity of the electrolyte in bulk, and

$$m = \frac{3 \cdot V_1 \cdot \chi}{\zeta \cdot V_2 \cdot R}$$

where V_1/V_2 is the ratio of the solid to liquid phases in the diaphragm (Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 69, 402; *Naturwiss.*, 1955, 42, 121); χ , the specific surface conductivity and R , the radius of the colloidal particles. It has been shown by Ghosh *et al.* (*Nature*, 1955, 176, 1080) that the equations of Booth (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 44, 955) and Henry (*ibid.*, 1948, 44, 1021) involving correction for surface conductance in electrophoresis also lead to an equation of the same form as (1) when kR is large, where k is the characteristic term of the Debye-Hückel equation and R represents the radius of the colloidal particles. The m in the electrophoretic equation is equal to $\chi/\zeta R$ and is, thus, different from the m in the equation for electro-osmosis.

Utilising equation (1), discussed above, attempts have been made to determine the true values of ζ -potential of lanthanum oxide sol in the regions of rapid and slow coagulation by the electro-osmotic and electrophoretic methods respectively. The results obtained are recorded in this communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Positively charged lanthanum oxide hydrosol was prepared in a way similar to that of Böhm and Niclassen (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 132, 6). To a 1% solution of lanthanum nitrate, in conductivity water, ammonia (1:3) was added till it was alkaline. The resulting voluminous white precipitate was washed and then peptised by the addition of $N/4$ -HCl. The opalescent sol, thus obtained, was dialysed in cellophane bags against conductivity water. The dialysis was performed for three weeks. After three weeks of ageing, experiments were started with the sol. Its lanthanum oxide content was 0.24% and the specific conductivity was 2.089×10^{-4} mhos at 35° .

Determination of the Equicoagulating Concentrations.—In experiments in the zone of rapid coagulation, an electrolyte solution (2 c.c.) was mixed with the colloid (2 c.c.). The mixture was left as such for 15 minutes and then it was centrifuged for 2 minutes at a definite speed. The supernatant solution was examined for transparency or opacity. The concentration of an electrolyte, which just gave a transparent supernatant solution, was taken as equicoagulating.

For the slow coagulation, the determination of the equicoagulating concentration was similar to that described above with this difference that the colloid-electrolyte mixture was allowed to stand undisturbed for 20 hours in place of 15 minutes.

Electro-osmotic Experiments

In the Zone of Rapid Coagulation.—A definite volume of electrolyte solution was added to an equal volume of the colloid so that the final concentration of the electrolyte in the mixture represented its equicoagulating concentration. After 15 minutes the mixture was centrifuged, the supernatant liquid was decanted into a Jena bottle and the coagula were transferred with a small amount of the supernatant liquid into a 'U' tube.

The diaphragm was prepared in the 'U' tube, by centrifuging for a definite period, and the volume occupied by it was maintained constant in all the experiments so that V_1 and V_2 of equation (1) remained constant. The supernatant liquid, obtained from the colloid-electrolyte mixture, was used for filling the U tube, and its specific conductivity was measured. The apparatus used for the measurement of the electrokinetic potential of the coagula of lanthanum oxide sol was similar to that used by Mukherjee *et al.* (*Nature*, 1922, 110, 732). The electro-osmotic experiments were carried out at 35° . The value of D was calculated from the empirical equation :

$$D = 80 - 0.4(t - 20^\circ).$$

The reproducibility of the electro-osmotic experiments was found to be within $\pm 3\%$.

TABLE I

Electro-osmotic data for rapid coagulation.

$$\zeta = 32.2 \text{ mv. } m = \frac{3V_1}{V_2} \cdot \frac{\chi}{\zeta R} = 1.449 \times 10^{-4}.$$

Electrolytes.	Equicoag. conc.	Sp. condy. of supernat. soln. at 35° ($S \times 10^4$).	Values of ζ_a calc. from	
			Smolnchowski eq.	Eq. (1).
NaCl	$1.014 \times 10^{-1} N$	125.400 mhos	32.0 mv	32.0 mv
Na ₂ SO ₄	3.943×10^{-4}	1.281	23.7	23.6
Na ₃ -citrate	3.908×10^{-4}	1.223	23.2	23.3
NaCl & Na ₂ SO ₄	2.303×10^{-2} & 2.069×10^{-4}	33.240	31.1	31.7
(I)				
NaCl & Na ₂ SO ₄	1.354×10^{-2} & 3.076×10^{-4}	3.086	28.3	27.9
(II)				

Electrophoretic Experiments

Since the measurement of ζ_a by the electro-osmotic method in the region of slow coagulation was not possible as a compact diaphragm of the coagula could not be prepared with NaCl and Na₃-citrate, hence electrophoretic method alone was used for the determination of ζ_a . For this purpose a modified form of Burton's U-tube apparatus was used. Each of the limbs of the U tube was provided with a stop-cock. The internal diameter of the upper and lower parts of the U tube was the same as that of the bore of the stop-cock. Two calomel electrode vessels were connected to the upper limbs through standard joints. The diameter of the nozzle of the electrode vessels above the joints was greater than that of the limbs of the U tube. Into the bottom of the U tube was sealed a fine, bent delivery tube, provided with a tap and a funnel, the level of the latter being higher than the top of the U tube.

The colloid-electrolyte mixture was prepared by addition of the electrolyte to the colloid, allowing it to stand for 30 minutes for attaining equilibrium, and then centrifuging for 2 minutes at a low speed to free the mixture of the precipitates. The lower part of the U tube and also the bore of the stop-cocks were filled with this turbid solution. The stop-cocks were then closed. The parts above the stop-cocks were then filled with the clear supernatant fluid, already prepared by rapid centrifuging of another lot of the colloid-electrolyte mixture after 20 hours of mixing. Two Ag/AgCl spiral electrodes were introduced into the calomel electrode vessels and the liquid was adjusted to the same level in them. The two stop-cocks were then opened very cautiously so that the boundaries between the colloid-electrolyte mixture and the supernatant solution remained sharp. The tap

in the delivery tube was carefully opened in order to allow the boundaries to rise in the vertical limbs and was closed when the boundary rose to a level about 2.5 cm above the stop-cocks. Electrical field was applied and a controlled current was allowed to flow through the system. The time required for the boundaries to travel a suitable distance was noted and from these and other relevant data, the electrophoretic velocities for upward and downward movements were calculated. The specific conductivity of the colloid-electrolyte mixture and that of the supernatant liquid were measured at the temperature of the experiment, their difference being within 3%. An average of the specific conductivities of the supernatant liquid and the colloid-electrolyte mixture was used throughout in the calculation of potential gradient. From this average specific conductance, the cross-sectional area of the limb, the velocity of moving boundary, the current, viscosity and dielectric constant of water at the temperature of the experiment, values of ζ_s were calculated from Smoluchowski's equation for upward and downward movements. Their average values are shown in Table II. The conductance of the supernatant solution was corrected for 29° since most of the experiments were performed at this temperature. Since $S\eta$ is constant, the value of ζ_s should be independent of temperature. In order to maintain the reversibility of Ag/AgCl electrodes during electrophoresis with Na_2SO_4 and $\text{Na}_3\text{-citrate}$, a small amount of NaCl was added (at the equicoagulating concentration of the mixture). When NaCl was used for coagulation, the upward and downward movements in the same set of experiments could not be performed due to partial coagulation. Hence, after the upward movement of the boundary was observed, the apparatus was dismantled and the liquid inside was discarded. Another similar experiment was carried out with the boundary made of a fresh colloid-electrolyte mixture of the same concentration as before. The current in this case was, however, allowed to pass in the reverse direction, and the rate of downward movement of the boundary was noted.

TABLE II

Electrophoretic data for slow coagulation.

$$\zeta = 35.1 \text{ mv. } m = \frac{\chi}{\zeta R} = 1.571 \times 10^{-6}.$$

Electrolytes.	Equicoag. conc.	Sp. condy. of supernat. soln. at 29° ($S \times 10^4$).	Values of ζ_s calculated from Smoluchowski eqn.			Eq. (1),
			Upward.	Downward.	Av.	
NaCl	$8.630 \times 10^{-2} N$	102.800 mhcs	34.2 mv	35.6 mv	34.9	34.9 mv
NaCl & Na_2SO_4	} (I) 1.354×10^{-2} & 2.740×10^{-4}	2.971	28.5	29.9	29.2	29.6
NaCl & Na_2SO_4						
NaCl & Na_2SO_4	} (II) 2.031×10^{-4} & 3.216×10^{-4}	1.446	25.0	25.5	25.3	25.4
NaCl & $\text{Na}_3\text{-citrate}$						
NaCl & $\text{Na}_3\text{-citrate}$	2.031×10^{-4} & 2.732×10^{-4}	1.356	24.4	25.2	24.8	24.9

DISCUSSION

It will appear from Fig. 1 that a plot of $1/\zeta_a$ against $1/S$ yields a straight line for the electro-osmotic measurements in the region of rapid coagulation as well as for the electrophoretic measurement in the region of slow coagulation. This linear relationship indicates that at the equicoagulating concentrations of the electrolytes used, the true ζ -potential and m remain constant under the conditions of the experiments.

FIG. 1

In the electro-osmotic experiments (Fig. 1) taking $m = 1.449 \times 10^{-6}$ and $1/\zeta = 0.0311$, the values of ζ_a have been calculated from equation (1) for the different values of S of the electrolytes used and are recorded in column 5 of Table I. It will be noticed that these values of ζ_a are in good agreement with those calculated from Smoluchowski's equation for the corresponding values of S (vide column 4 of Table I). In the region of slow coagulation (Fig. 1) taking $m = 1.571 \times 10^{-6}$ and $1/\zeta = 0.0215$, the values of ζ_a from electrophoretic data for the different values of S , corresponding to various electrolytes used, have been calculated from equation (1) and are recorded in column 7 of Table II. There is fair agreement between these values of ζ_a and the average of those calculated from Smoluchowski's equation for the corresponding values of S .

As the values of true ζ are the same for all electrolytes for a particular rate of coagulation, it may be concluded that a given rate of coagulation of the sol is characterised by a definite value of true ζ -potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used.

It will also be noticed that the difference in the values of true ζ , found for rapid and slow rates of coagulation, is not much (35.1-32.2 mv). Therefore it may be concluded that there is a critical zone of ζ -potential for the coagulation of this sol by electrolytes.